

Towards Sustainable Horticulture in the Himalayas: A Development Framework from Uttarakhand, India

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Abstract- Uttarakhand, a Himalayan state that recently completed 24 years of its formation, stands at a critical juncture where inclusive growth must align with its unique agro-ecological strengths. Agriculture supports over 70 percent of the population yet contributes only 12.36 percent to the State's GDP due to fragmented landholdings, difficult terrain, low mechanization, and weak market infrastructure. Within this context, horticulture has emerged as a sector of comparative advantage, contributing nearly 30 percent to agriculture's GDP. The state's diverse agro-climatic conditions enable the cultivation of high-value fruits such as apple, peach, plum, kiwi, and dragon fruit, alongside vegetables, floriculture, and medicinal plants. However, Uttarakhand's farmers face significant challenges including post-harvest losses, poor supply chains, inadequate training, and income disparity compared to farmers in Himachal Pradesh and Jammu & Kashmir.

This paper proposes a sustainable horticulture development framework structured in three stages: indigenization and multiplication of quality planting material, technology transfer through Self-help Groups (SHGs) and training of extension agents, and establishment of farmer-led market hubs linking producers, agribusiness experts, and consumers. The framework emphasizes cost-effective technology adoption, professionalization of horticulture, and value addition through processing and branding. Strengthening horticulture as an agribusiness-driven model can generate livelihoods, enhance farmer incomes, and establish Uttarakhand as a "Green Organic State."

Keywords: Horticulture, Sustainable Horticulture Development, Indigenization of Technology, Agro-climatic zones, Protected Cultivation and Uttarakhand.

1. Introduction

Uttarakhand, having completed 24 years as a separate state, is now poised to embark on a new era of rapid and inclusive growth and all-round development. Uttarakhand is primarily an agricultural state although its share in the country's total area and production is exceedingly small. The low agricultural yield reflects the small size and scattered land holdings, difficult terrain, low use of quality seeds, lack of or inadequate availability of improved inputs and technology, lack of extension, low farm mechanization and lack of credit and marketing facilities. The contribution of agriculture to the state's gross domestic product is about 12.36 per cent and the population dependent on agriculture for their livelihood is more than 70 per cent. The staple crops, wheat and paddy cover 30 per cent and 26 per cent of the gross cropped

area, respectively. The horticulture sector (along with food processing) accounts for 30 percent of the total contribution of the agriculture sector to the State's GDP. Other important crops include sugarcane, maize, finger-millet, barnyard-millet, pulses, and oilseeds. Horticulture crops cover 2.97 lakh ha out of the 6.21 lakh ha total cropped area. Major fruits produced include mango, litchi, guava, and apple, while vegetables like potato, tomato, green pea, cauliflower, and capsicum are significant (**National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development, 2024**). The Horticulture Mission for North-East and Himalayan states (HMNEH) is a major program under which huge financial support was allocated for the purpose of development of horticulture sector in the state of Uttarakhand (**Kumar et al. 2021**).

Rural development framework of hills of Uttarakhand if it must be sustainable has to go through the local strength and resources of hilly areas. The positive features of these hill districts are that they have enormous potential, a suitable climate for high-value agriculture, and a pleasant environment due to 60 per cent forest cover (**Mittal et al., 2008**). These must be harnessed for a development strategy. The varied agro-climatic zones create a conducive environment for the cultivation of a wide variety of horticultural crops. Subtropical climate zone is suitable for Mango, guava and papaya. Cultivation of citrus crops is appropriate in the valleys and mid-altitudes. Temperate zone is suitable for a wide variety of fruits which include apples, pear, peach, walnut, apricot and plum. Among vegetables, the high latitudes are favorable for potato cultivation, mid-altitudes for tomato cultivation, while ginger is a suitable crop to grow in both subtropical and temperate zones. Flowers can also be cultivated in all altitudinal zones (**Sati, 2018**). To change the economic and social backwardness in these hill districts it is important to adopt a strategy based on long-term planning. Thus, the objective is to identify sectors where these hill districts have a comparative advantage and prepare a strategy. This paper proposes a strategy for a planned approach to rapid growth of the hill districts with a vision to include both human and economic development supported with environmental conservation suitable for hill agriculture. The development of horticulture and a horticulture-based system that is linked with the growth of industries can be the way towards development of the hill regions. This agribusiness promotion-based development strategy for Uttarakhand hills has an insight to develop brand equity under the name of Green Organic State.

2. Horticulture in Uttarakhand: Strengths, Opportunities, and Challenges

It is the first state, practicing organic farming on a wide scale. The positive features of these hill districts are that they have a suitable climate for high value agriculture, potential development of horticulture, agro-processing industries, organic farming, off-season vegetable cultivation and huge tourism potential. As per the production statistics of key crops (**Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, 2022**), Uttarakhand ranks first in peach production with a 48.88 per cent share of national production, it holds first place in plum production contributing 44.40 per cent to the country's production, ranked second in walnut production with a 6.71 per cent share, while Jammu & Kashmir leads at 91.68 per cent. It has third position nationwide with a 2.66 per cent share, significantly trailing behind Jammu & Kashmir at 70.54 per cent, it also so ranks third in pear production with a substantial 26.40 per cent share, behind Jammu & Kashmir at 29.76 per cent. Protected cultivation of horticultural crops has observed

high income potential in Uttarakhand with support of the schemes like State Horticulture Mission scheme, schemes of National Horticulture Board, etc. to promote the protected cultivation in the state (**Kumar et al. 2021**). Uttarakhand has conducive agro-climatic conditions and high production potential for production of horticultural crops like the states of Himachal-Pradesh and Jammu & Kashmir; however, the annual income of the commercial farmers of Kashmir and Himachal Pradesh is three times more than that of the subsistence hill farmers in Uttarakhand. Thus, there is a huge disparity in the annual incomes of Himalayan farming families burdened with fragmented landholdings, major supply chain issues, post-harvest losses, poor marketing infrastructure and lack of training, infrastructure facility and collaboration amongst the stakeholders (**Lamba and Mittal, 2020**). Looking into the high demand, revenue potential, hardiness, long shelf-life and less vulnerability to wild animals, Uttarakhand has identified and targeted the large-scale cultivation of two high-value fruit crops, i.e., Kiwi and Dragon-fruit. Uttarakhand Kiwi Policy 2025 envisioned till 2030-31 has been launched with the total project outlay of Rs. 894 crores. As per the Ministry of Commerce, Government of India, the demand of kiwi fruit in India is increasing significantly. About 75 per cent demand is being fulfilled through import of kiwi fruit that has enhanced from 49,483 Mt to 64,779 Mt in 2021–2022. Similarly, Dragon fruit Mission has been launched in the State in April 2025 till 2027-28, to support the farmers with 80 per cent financial assistance in cultivating dragon fruit using modern and scientific methods (**ANI News, 2022; TOI, 2025**). The financial aid and support provided by the government is utmost important for boosting the horticultural production and income of the farmers, however, there must be a framework that can make the horticultural farming sustainable in Uttarakhand for farmers to fetch remunerative prices. Farmers' Self-help groups can be instrumental in overcoming the barrier of fragmented landholding, lack of negotiation ability, decision-making ability, credit worthiness, market support and fulfilling the training need of the farmers in hilly areas.

3. Sustainable Horticulture Development Framework for Uttarakhand State

The proposed framework is divided into three steps. The first section outlines the indigenization of technology and plant material multiplication. The second step discusses the transfer of technology through Self-help groups (SHGs) and training of the extension agents as well as farmers. The third step gives the linking of the SHGs chain, secondary producers and consumers creating a market hub focusing on the horticulture in respect to Uttarakhand region. It also focuses on strategies to help farmers to become quality conscious and more entrepreneurial-minded, i.e., more flexible, and creative in their farming. As depicted in Figure 1, the first circle talks about a center acting as a Horti-Technology hub ex., Holland functioned as hub for the Indo-Dutch horticulture project in Uttarakhand. The process of technology transfer from the hub will be supported by input supply necessary for the technology development in the state for example planting material for cut flower production from Holland require infrastructure development like poly houses etc. under the guidance of agri-business expert. This process of technology transfer is followed by indigenization of the technology.

This indigenization of technology is based upon the socio-economic & cultural grassroots realities. The process of indigenization of technology focuses on the conversion of adopted

technology according to the ecological, geographical conditions of Uttarakhand hills and the varied economic conditions of the people. This indigenization accounts for simplification of technology making it cost effective so that it is accessible to a wider range of users in Uttarakhand. Moreover, this simplification needs to be done by setting up of R&D unit for the simplification of the technology and hardware development required to support the indigenized technology. The work will be carried out under the supervision of local experts well acquainted with the conditions and agribusiness experts.

Simplification of imported technology is made cost effective to make it feasible for maximum farmers to adopt it as “Technology transfer is the process of sharing of skills, knowledge, technologies, methods of manufacturing, samples of manufacturing and facilities among governments and other institutions to ensure that scientific and technological developments are accessible to a wider range of users who can then further develop and exploit the technology into new products, processes, applications, materials or services.” Following this definition multiplication of the planting material is done at the R&D centers. This will help in achieving self-dependency in planting material development and thus reduce the import expenditures by increasing cost-effectiveness and resource strengthening.

Figure 1. Horticulture based framework for sustainable agricultural development.

The tested and adapted technology then needs to be transferred to actual growers, i.e., technology commercialization needs to be done. This technology transfer to grassroots will be taken up by the formation of a chain of SHGs linked together and through proper training of the local experts and farmers in various aspects of development. Collaboration and Support from all the agencies across the food supply chain was considered an important factor to overcome the food loss and wastage in environmentally sustainable ways (Sharma *et al.*, 2022). All SHGs are required to work together with local experts. The planting material

developed by these links will be provided with market support or a market linkage where the product is made available in the market for secondary producers, for local markets and for export. The planting materials converted to value added products are again brought to the marketing outlets for the local market as well as exports headed by agribusiness experts thus creating a farmer-led market hub linking farmers, secondary producers, agribusiness experts, market supported by R&D.

This framework may have the following impacts on the hills of Uttarakhand:

- With the state's favorable climate for horticulture, the integration of technology will enable optimal resource use and significantly enhance production, offering a comparative advantage over traditional crops.
- Adapting and simplifying technology to socio-economic and geographical conditions will ensure cost-effectiveness and promote the transition from traditional to modern agriculture at the grassroots level.
- Capacity-building and training will foster professionalism in horticultural enterprises, moving beyond subsistence cultivation.
- Increased quality awareness at the grassroots will lead to higher-grade produce, better market access, and export opportunities.
- Local development of quality planting material will reduce dependence on imports, save foreign exchange, and ensure better produce for domestic consumers.
- The promotion of horticulture-based entrepreneurial skills among hill farmers will generate employment opportunities within the region.
- Linking SHGs with markets and agribusiness experts will minimize the role of intermediaries and ensure direct benefits reach farmers.

4. Conclusion

Uttarakhand with its ample natural resources, favorable natural conditions, and immense potential to emerge as a hotspot of livelihood opportunities must undergo strategic transformation. Based on the perception of farmers and analyses of key-stakeholders the paper identified Horticulture as the sector having comparative advantage in the region due to its agro-climatic conditions. The development strategy for the Uttarakhand hills should be based on developing the horticulture-based framework of rural development through strategy of agri-horti agribusiness network with emphasis on planting material development. It was also understood through the study that the rural development framework of hills of Uttarakhand if it must be sustainable has to go through the local strength and resources of hilly areas. Considering and identifying the roles of stakeholders like Input dealers, Agri-business experts, local experts, SHGs, extension functionaries and farmers, the study proposes a sustainable agriculture development framework for Uttarakhand state. It also includes the role of agricultural advisory services to further the development. It promotes channels between human resources, natural resources, the local business communities in to furthering entrepreneurial activities. The development of horticulture and a horticulture-based system that is linked with the growth of industries can be the way towards development of the hill regions. This

agribusiness promotion-based development strategy for Uttarakhand hills has an insight to develop brand equity under the name of Green Organic State.

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